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D7.5 – Blue-Cloud 2026 Sustainability Strategy & Plan

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
AI/ML	Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning
CRL	Commercial Readiness Level
EDITO	European Digital Twin Ocean
EIF	EOSC Interoperability Framework
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOV	Essential Ocean Variables
ICOOE	Integration of Coastal Ocean Observations along Europe
IOC	Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission
IRL	Integrated Readiness Level
KER	Key Exploitable Result
MEI	Marine Environmental Indicators
OBPS	Ocean Best Practices System
OTGA	Ocean Teacher Global Academy
OA	Ocean Acidification
R&I	Research and Innovation
SBEP	Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership
SDI	Spatial Data Infrastructure
SRL	Societal Readiness Level
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UN	United Nations
Vlab	Virtual Lab
VRE	Virtual Research Environment

Keywords

Blue-Cloud; Business Model; EDITO; EMODnet; EOSC; EOSC Node; Sustainability Plan; Marine Services; Workbenches; Virtual Labs.

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Executive Summary

Blue-Cloud 2026 builds on the successful foundations of the original Blue-Cloud initiative and its continued evolution into a federated marine data and analytics ecosystem supporting Open Science and the European Ocean digital infrastructure. The initiative integrates and extends best practices, tools and services developed through previous European Union funded projects, as well as relevant EOSC-related initiatives and community-driven developments, including work on interoperability, FAIR data principles, and research infrastructure integration.

By enabling FAIR data management and federated access across marine scientific domains, Blue-Cloud 2026 strengthens collaboration among research infrastructures, thematic communities, and stakeholder groups at European and international level. This approach enhances the accessibility, interoperability, and reuse of marine research outputs, while fostering the development and uptake of innovative cloud-based services, Virtual Labs and Workbenches that support multidisciplinary ocean science.

Through the translation and operationalisation of FAIR-enabling solutions across marine disciplines, the project contributes to improved scientific collaboration, reproducibility and data-driven discovery in ocean science. These advances also reinforce trust in digital research infrastructures and support higher-quality, more efficient research workflows across the blue economy and environmental policy domains.

This report outlines the sustainability planning for each one of the Blue-Cloud 2026 key outputs identified as critical for the European marine data ecosystem and the wider EOSC landscape. Whether maintained as operational services, integrated into larger infrastructures such as EOSC and EDITO, or sustained by partner organisations and community stakeholders, these outputs are intended to continue shaping best practices, interoperability frameworks and policy alignment for a long-term, sustainable European marine digital ecosystem.

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1. Introduction

This deliverable, *D7.5 Sustainability Strategy & Plan*, outlines the approach adopted by Blue-Cloud 2026 to ensure the long-term continuity, accessibility, and impact of each one of its results beyond the lifetime of the project, which concludes in June 2026. Building on the foundations established in previous iterations of Blue-Cloud 2026, the strategy focuses on transforming project outputs, such as federated data services, Virtual Labs and Workbenches, as well as other thematic applications, into sustainable assets embedded within the broader European marine and digital research ecosystem. This document also provides a structured framework for assessing and enhancing sustainability across multiple dimensions, including technological integration, governance, community uptake, and alignment with European initiatives such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the Digital Twin Ocean (EDITO).

2. The Context: positioning EOSC Node | European Digital Twin Ocean in the framework of the European Digital Twin Ocean

The sustainability of Blue-Cloud 2026 is defined by a clear evolutionary path from a pilot Research & Innovation (R&I) initiative to a permanent, operational component of the European marine data landscape. This transition ensures that the federated ecosystem developed for oceans and waters is integrated into the official **EOSC Federation** and the **European Digital Twin Ocean**.

2.1. The Path: From Blue-Cloud 2026 VRE to the EOSC Node

The journey begins with the **Blue-Cloud 2026 Virtual Research Environment (VRE)**, powered by the D4Science platform, which has successfully piloted a "de facto" marine thematic node for EOSC between 2019 and 2026. The strategic goal is now to formalize this into the operational **EOSC Node European Digital Twin Ocean**, serving as the official thematic entry point for the marine community within the wider EOSC ecosystem.

To achieve a cohesive digital environment for the **EU Mission: Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030**, a "Smart Federation" is required between the established Blue-Cloud VRE and the **EDITO** core infrastructure platform of the European Digital Twin of the Ocean. This federation ensures the mutual exposure of analytical processes, allowing researchers to build and run complex, data-intensive workflows across both platforms seamlessly. The technical strategy for **Functional Interoperability** between D4Science and EDITO is not merely about data exchange but about **Resource Orchestration**. By aligning with the **EOSC Interoperability Framework (EIF)**, the EOSC Node ensures that the Marine Knowledge value chain remains auditable and reproducible across the federation, fulfilling the mandate for **Radical Transparency**.

2.2. Research & Integration: The EOSC-Marine Project

The newly funded **EOSC-Marine project** (HORIZON-INFRA-2025-01 - GA 101292903) starting in September 2026, serves as the R&I vehicle to implement this integration. Coordinated by CNR, under the name “**EOSC Node European Digital Twin Ocean**” will evolve into the component of EDITO that delivers EOSC FAIR Open data and analytical services, focusing on two key pillars:

- **Radical Transparency:** The project implements high-level provenance tracking based on W3C-PROV specifications. This ensures "Radical Transparency" across the entire marine data value chain—from raw observations to digital twin outputs—thereby increasing scientific trust and reproducibility;
- **Functional Interoperability:** It advances the technical alignment between D4Science and EDITO by harmonizing Authentication, Authorization, and Accounting (AAI) and exposing computational processes via standardized OGC APIs.

2.3. Operationalization for Sustainability: EDITO Phase 3

While the EOSC-Marine project drives the research, the **EDITO** action provides the mechanism for long-term operationalization. This phase requires that the European Digital Twin Ocean becomes a fully operational public service by 2030. Within this framework, **CNR** is specifically tasked with:

- **Node Deployment:** Establishing the EOSC Node European Digital Twin Ocean within the public EDITO core, leveraging the methodological developments from Blue-Cloud and the EOSC-Marine project;
- **Scaling & Performance:** Scaling up Cloud and HPC services to support complex, high-resolution oceanographic modeling and AI-driven analysis;
- **Pre-operational Services:** Establishing automated operational pipelines to prevent the obsolescence of tools and validating "quality-labeled" applications for critical marine management areas such as fisheries, biodiversity, and Marine Spatial Planning.

By splitting these efforts between a dedicated R&I project (**EOSC-Marine**) for technical integration and a public infrastructure action (**European Digital Twin Ocean - EDITO**) for operational scaling, the sustainability of Blue-Cloud’s legacy is secured as a cornerstone of the future European Digital Twin Ocean. The **EOSC Node European Digital Twin Ocean** will support the development of applications that could be later deployed on EDITO for sustainability.

3. From Assets to Impact: Sustainability of Blue-Cloud Federated Assets up to 2030

As Blue-Cloud 2026 evolves from a project-driven initiative into a lasting component of the European marine and environmental research ecosystem, ensuring the sustainability of its federated assets

becomes a critical priority. The value generated through Blue-Cloud 2026 extends beyond the development of technical infrastructures, services, and datasets. It lies in their continued ability to support scientific excellence, innovation, policy-making and the sustainable blue economy. This chapter examines the pathways through which Blue-Cloud 2026 key exploitable results will remain operational, relevant, and impactful up to 2030 and beyond. It explores the mechanisms needed to transform project outputs into enduring resources that continue to deliver value to stakeholders across Europe.

3.1 Sustainability Pathways (Research, Policy, Commercial and Societal)

The long-term sustainability of Blue-Cloud assets depends not only on maintaining technical infrastructure but also on ensuring their continued relevance and uptake across diverse stakeholder communities. Sustainability can be achieved through multiple, interconnected pathways that reflect the broad range of value generated by Blue-Cloud. This section explores the long-term viability of Blue-Cloud assets, creating mutually reinforcing mechanisms that extend their impact and ensure their continued contribution to Europe's sustainable ocean agenda.

Name of service	Brief description	Why it needs to be sustained - Unique value proposition
Core Services	This asset comprises the foundational infrastructure layer, including the Identity Management (AAI), the Global Resource Catalogue, and the Accounting/Monitoring systems. These services are powered by the D4Science platform and act as the orchestrator for the Smart Federation, ensuring seamless interoperability between the EOSC Node European DTO and the broader European data landscape (EDITO, EOSC Federation)	The Core Services represent the glue of the marine data ecosystem. Sustaining this asset is vital because it provides a single, unified entry point (AAI and Global Catalogue) to a highly fragmented landscape of marine data providers. Its unique value lies in the Smart Federation capability, which allows researchers to discover and use resources across different infrastructures without needing multiple credentials or complex data transfers. Without this orchestrator, the cross-domain synergy between EOSC and the marine community would revert to isolated silos
Generic Services	This category includes the Virtual Research Environments (VREs) and interactive computing tools like JupyterLab and RStudio. A key evolving component of this asset is the AI-ready analytical environment, which will provide the marine community with access to a dedicated GPU farm (up to 50 GPUs by 2027). This infrastructure is	These services empower the environment where data becomes knowledge. The unique value is the provision of pre-configured, collaborative analytical environments (VREs, Cloud Computing Platform, and JupyterHub) that are directly co-located with marine data streams. By sustaining this, the project provides a cost-effective alternative to commercial clouds, specifically through the

Name of service	Brief description	Why it needs to be sustained - Unique value proposition
	<p>specifically designed to support the execution of Large Language Models (LLMs) and complex machine learning workflows directly over marine datasets. This is complemented by data lake technology that enables users to efficiently access, subset, analyze, and harmonise large datasets.</p>	<p>planned institutional GPU farm (50 units by 2027). This enables researchers to run complex AI/ML models on massive datasets without the prohibitive compute costs associated with general-purpose cloud providers</p>
<p>SDI Facilities</p>	<p>The Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) consists of cataloguing and visualization services (e.g., GeoNetwork, GeoServer) that enable the discovery and processing of geospatial ocean data. These facilities are maintained to be natively compatible with EMODnet and EDITO Datalab standards, allowing GIS projects and maps created within Blue-Cloud to be utilized within the wider European Digital Twin Ocean ecosystem without further data conversion</p>	<p>The SDI facilities are the essential bridge for visual discovery and standard-compliant data sharing. Their sustainability ensures that the results generated within Blue-Cloud VREs are not lost in private folders but are instead natively interoperable with EMODnet and EDITO. The unique value proposition is the standardization-by-design approach, which ensures that any geospatial product created by a scientist is immediately ready for consumption by European decision-makers and the Digital Twin Ocean infrastructure</p>
<p>Coastal Currents Observations Vlab</p>	<p>The Coastal Currents from Observations Virtual Lab offers users to generate integrated ocean surface current maps by merging data from multiple sources. It uses direct and indirect current measurements, including High Frequency (HF) radar, drifter observations, and geostrophic currents derived from satellite altimetry. The integration relies on the DIVAnd (Data Interpolating Variational Analysis in n dimensions) method, which applies physical constraints such as coastline boundaries, horizontal divergence, and momentum balance to improve the reliability of the output.</p>	<p>Ocean surface currents are the fundamental engine of regional basin dynamics, dictating the transport and distribution of heat, salinity, nutrients, and dissolved gases. As the primary horizontal drivers, they influence the trajectory of all marine tracers, directly impacting ecosystem health, primary productivity, and the dispersal of pollutants or marine debris. Sustaining Vab2 that integrates multi-source observations, such as HF radar, drifters, and altimetry, is critical because it bridges the gap between different data types to provide a coherent, physically consistent product. By utilizing the DIVAnd method to incorporate essential constraints like momentum balance and coastline boundaries, the lab ensures a coherent dynamical view of the ocean currents. This integrated approach is highly beneficial for operational safety,</p>

Name of service	Brief description	Why it needs to be sustained - Unique value proposition
<p>Global Fisheries Atlas Vlab</p>	<p>The <i>Global Fisheries Atlas</i> Virtual Lab offers an integrated view of global fisheries to support decision-making and resource management. It follows recognised standards for data and knowledge management, and it remains accessible to users interested in fisheries data, whether for research, policy, or general understanding.</p>	<p>climate monitoring, and the effective management of regional maritime resources.</p> <p>Fisheries data are a unique source for biological EOv in the global ocean. Tuna fisheries are among the most important fisheries worldwide. Tuna fisheries data can be used as a pilot project to showcase how FAIRness of fisheries data can be improved and help better manage marine ecosystems. Methods and tools developed for this use case are generic enough to be used for other fisheries and species.</p>
<p>Integration of coastal ocean observations along Europe Vlab</p>	<p>The Integration of Coastal Ocean Observations along Europe (ICOOE) Virtual Lab offers a platform for accessing, exploring, integrating, and visualizing coastal ocean observations across Europe. It focuses on data collected by the Joint European Research Infrastructure for Coastal Observatories (JERICO-RI) and other European Blue Data Infrastructures, as well as on model results available at CMEMS. It supports users through 3 Thematic Services aimed to facilitate the study of coastal processes such as biological connectivity, contaminant dispersion, the assessment of the impacts of extreme events or the exploration of the add-value of glider observations.</p>	<p>Advancing the understanding of coastal ocean processes requires the analysis and integration of diversified datasets. ICOOE aims to help users in this goal, in particular in coping with relevant data dispersed through different aggregators and with the diversified range of formats and specificities of the datasets. The available pilot demonstrator focuses on a specific regional domain (Iberian Margin area) and on specific variables (currents, waves, glider measurements) or time periods (selected extreme events). Application and limited development of the demonstrator is planned in the framework of the European project AQUARIUS. Sustaining ICOOE will enable to reach the full the potential of the service, namely to expand it (1) to provide a broad geographical area of application (global European coverage, global coastal ocean areas),(2) to cover a broad range of variables, (3) to implement specific tools to explore interfaces between the coastal ocean and the inland waters, the deep ocean waters and the atmosphere, and (4) to provide a broad range of products to support researchers, Blue Economy agents, decision makers and general public. These developments are also key to</p>

Name of service	Brief description	Why it needs to be sustained - Unique value proposition
<p>Carbon-Plankton Dynamics Vlab</p>	<p>The Carbon-Plankton Dynamics Virtual Lab provides a modelling environment to simulate interactions between nutrients, phytoplankton, zooplankton, and detritus in marine ecosystems. At its core is a Nutrient-Phytoplankton-Zooplankton-Detritus (NPZD) model that runs in both nitrogen and carbon units, enabling consistent tracking of carbon flows through various ecosystem processes.</p>	<p>promote a close interaction with the JERICO community.</p> <p>The VLab benefits from the support of EU initiatives, most notably EMODnet and ICOS, which provides the underlying data required to run the model, ensuring continuity and long-term availability of the service. The underpinning script has been made openly available on GitHub, reinforcing a commitment to open science and reproducibility. Notably, the model can also be executed within the European Digital Twin Ocean environment, establishing a direct and meaningful link between the two platforms and demonstrating the VLab's capacity to operate across complementary European research infrastructures.</p>
<p>Marine Environmental Indicators Vlab</p>	<p>The Marine Environmental Indicators (MEI) VLab enables users to monitor and evaluate the environmental conditions of marine areas, providing essential support for decision-making in ocean management. By integrating multiple data sources, the platform offers a unified data analysis service, facilitating online computation of indicators through Jupyter Notebooks or a dedicated web application. This application leverages the VRE Analytics Engine services to generate indicator outputs. VLab 4 represents four indicators Ocean Heat Content (OHC), Eutrophication (TRIX), Marine Heatwaves (MHW), Storm Severity Index (SSI v2)) as well as web application.</p>	<p>This service is essential for the decision makers and provides an integrated and consistent view to indicators through a single entry point which is fully integrated with the other Blue-Cloud services, offering in this way an effective and sustainable solution, not only to decision makers, but also to the developers for the implementation of new environmental indicators.</p>
	<p>The ecosystem-level EOV provides a standardized modelling framework critical to predict biogeographic patterns</p>	<p>This publicly available service is a versatile machine learning tool that can be used to not only extrapolate biological information to the</p>

Name of service	Brief description	Why it needs to be sustained - Unique value proposition
<p>Ecosystem-level EOVs WB</p>	<p>in space and time and across the diverse range of emergent biological sampling methods aiming to diagnose biological EOVs. In response, we introduce CEPHALOPOD (Comprehensive Ensemble Pipeline for Habitat modelling Across Large-scale Ocean Pelagic Observation Datasets), a standardized, highly automated and flexible framework designed to integrate and analyse heterogeneous marine data for multi-species habitat modelling following best practices in the field. CEPHALOPOD is built on observational data from federating initiatives such as AtlantECO, OBIS, GBIF, associated with already existing statistical and machine learning methods that enable users to extract and model information from heterogeneous, scarce and biased field observations. It is highly automated and follows explicit quality checks informing the user of the predictive accuracy and interpretability of the results.</p>	<p>global scale, but any geo-referenced ocean EOVS, including those produced by other WBs. It can handle binary, continuous and also relative data, and can thus be applied to a wide variety of EOVS, and it comes with a uniquely comprehensive uncertainty analysis and a rigorous quality control assessment. Due to its flexibility and transferability to a wide range of data types and problems, it will benefit substantially from the exponentially increasing data availability across all major data repositories, and is likely to give more and more accurate projections with time. Through its embedding into eosc-Marine, it will access an even wider digital ecosystem of biodiversity and ecosystem data repositories, including MGnify, which will increase its usefulness, and open its functionality to a wide range of new variables, including new and interesting biomolecules, data on biodiversity from metabarcoding, ecosystem structure from metagenomics, ecosystem functioning from metatranscriptomics, etc. It may also be paired with existing and future climate model projections to be able to project the impact of climate change on marine ecosystems. It will thus serve policy makers, ecosystem managers and conservationists in decision making processes, as well as scientists, museum staff and others to build a graphic atlas of plankton biogeography, marine ecosystem composition and their changes under different future climates.</p>
<p>Eutrophication:</p>	<p>The Eutrophication Workbench (EWB) provides an efficient workflow to merge, aggregate, and harmonise multi-source in situ datasets from EMODnet Chemistry, the Copernicus Marine Service, and the World Ocean Database</p>	<p>The core value of the Eutrophication Workbench (EWB) lies in its ability to transform fragmented, multi-source marine observations into a consistent, high-quality, fully harmonized and standardized data stream. Sustaining this VLab is essential to</p>

Name of service	Brief description	Why it needs to be sustained - Unique value proposition
<p>chlorophyll, nutrients, oxygen WB</p>	<p>(WOD) into high-quality collections targeting key Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs): chlorophyll-a, nutrients, and dissolved oxygen. Operating within a cloud-based Virtual Laboratory (VLab), the workflow leverages Beacon, a high-performance data lake engine for rapid data subsetting and cross-infrastructure harvesting, alongside webODV for interactive data exploration, visualization, and validation. To ensure data integrity across multiple sources, the workflow embeds the CW duplicate tool (CWdt) to identify duplicate records, and File Forge to filter records according to prefixed rules, clean, and transform data into three primary computational formats. The result is a transparent, reproducible, and scientifically controlled workflow from raw data lakes to analysis-ready products.</p>	<p>bypass the systemic inefficiencies of manual data curation, such as cleaning, formatting, and deduplication across incompatible big data infrastructures, thereby optimising workflows for the direct benefit of both the scientific community and policy makers. The resulting high-quality collections of key Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) are of direct interest for EMODnet, Copernicus Marine, and EDITO.</p>
<p>Physics: temperature & salinity WB</p>	<p>The Physics Workbench Lab enables users to integrate Temperature and Salinity data from four BDIs: SeaDataNet, Copernicus Marine Service (CORA product), EuroArgo and World Ocean DataBase, leveraging Beacon. The data integration includes semantic harmonization of a set of essential metadata variables, which uses a semantic analyser service in combination with Beacon. The integrated data-lake allows data and metadata sub-set or filtering. The extracted data pass through an additional quality control process to guarantee data quality consistency and potential duplicates are detected and handled. The result is an added value</p>	<p>This service is important for EOVs data integration in a digital ecosystem landscape where multiple data infrastructures or research infrastructures manage data. Through a federated approach, new BDIs can be federated and EOVs data integrated. This allows the maximization of data to be used for developing new knowledge and information to multiple intermediaries and end-users. The derived products (monitoring indicators) will have enhanced accuracy. The full traceability and provenance preservation will enable a continuous assessment of EOVs data availability at global scale and its distribution in terms of data providers, instruments and platforms.</p>

Name of service	Brief description	Why it needs to be sustained - Unique value proposition
	EOVs dataset ready to be used for assimilation in ocean reanalysis, for deriving multi-year data products, such as climate normals and the Ocean Heat Content (OHC) indicator of MEI VLab. The dataset can also be used for AI data driven applications.	

Table 1 Blue-Cloud 2026 Key Exploitable Results (KER)

3.1.2 Integrated Readiness Level

The overall maturity of each exploitable result is assessed through an Integrated Readiness Level (IRL), which combines Technology Readiness Level (TRL), Societal Readiness Level (SRL), and Commercial Readiness Level (CRL). This integrated approach provides a comprehensive measure of an asset's capacity to generate sustainable impact and aligns with the Horizon Europe framework for monitoring innovation uptake and impact pathways. The **TRL** is a systematic metric used to assess the maturity of a technology, while the **SRL** measures the degree to which an innovation is understood, accepted, adopted, and integrated by its intended users and stakeholders. **CRL** evaluates the market maturity and business viability of an innovation. It considers factors such as value proposition, market demand, customer validation, business model development, intellectual property management, investment readiness, revenue potential, and scalability.

Name of service	TRL	SRL	CRL	Current Stage and Next Steps (Blue-Cloud funds)	Current users	Geographical relevance
Core Services	9	8	7	<i>Current:</i> Production-ready environment supporting the Global Resource Catalogue and AAI. <i>Next Steps:</i> Implementing full technical alignment with the EOSC EU Node reference architecture and finalizing the 'Smart Federation' with EDITO	2900+ registered users across multiple VREs	European-wide with global reach through international collaborations
Generic Services	8	8	5	<i>Current:</i> CCP, JupyterLab, and RStudio environments operational.	2900+ registered users across multiple VREs	European research community, specifically

Name of service	TRL	SRL	CRL	Current Stage and Next Steps (Blue-Cloud funds)	Current users	Geographical relevance
				<i>Next Steps:</i> Integration of LLM-powered discovery assistants and the initial rollout of the federated GPU farm to support high-performance marine analytics.		targeting AI/ML modelers in oceanography.
SDI Facilities	9	8	6	<i>Current:</i> Operational GeoServer/GeoNetwork instances. <i>Next Steps:</i> Enhancing metadata cross-walking to ensure full discoverability of Blue-Cloud GIS layers within the EDITO DTO and EMODnet catalogues	Marine data managers, GIS specialists, and researchers producing geospatial data products within the VREs	Pan-European (aligned with INSPIRE and FAIR principles)
Coastal Currents Observations Vlab	8	8	1	Operational	Students in oceanography, data scientists for fisheries purposes, marine scientists	Mediterranean Sea
Global Fisheries Atlas Vlab	8	8	5	Operational Yearly updates of data and code created in the VLab are also published on Zenodo (also GitHub for the code) and FAO SDI. Containerization of the data generation workflow, RStudio and Shiny apps successfully deployed on D4Science and EDITO.	Fisheries science, marine ecology	Global ocean
Integration of coastal ocean observations along Europe Vlab	7	4-5	1	<i>Current:</i> Service operational for a pilot demonstrator offering 3 thematic services focussed on the Iberian Margin area. <i>Next Steps:</i> Development towards service for global geographical area and full range of variables	Researchers Blue-economy users General Public	Current: Pilot demonstrator for Iberian Margin area. Next Steps: Implementation for general geographical domain

Name of service	TRL	SRL	CRL	Current Stage and Next Steps (Blue-Cloud funds)	Current users	Geographical relevance
						(global European margin, global coastal ocean areas)
Carbon-Plankton Dynamics Vlab	7	5	1	Operational	Students in marine ecology, marine scientists	Belgian Part of the North Sea and Adriatic Sea
Marine Environmental Indicators Vlab	8	7	1	<i>Current:</i> Operational. Services for indicator generation available through Jupyter notebooks, Webapp, CCP. <i>Next:</i> evolving as framework inside EOSC Marine to easily incorporate new indicators	400+ registered users	Mediterranean sea
Ecosystem-level EOVs WB	8	5	n/a	Fully operational within the BlueCloud2026 environment and also within local installation. <i>Next steps:</i> Testing within EOSC-Marine project; further integration with data lakes desirable.	WB partners; 15+ scientific ongoing collaborations	global surface ocean
Eutrophication: chlorophyll, nutrients, oxygen WB	7	3	1	<i>Current stage:</i> Operational. <i>Next steps (EOSC-Marine funds):</i> Exploit the WB results within EMODnet and EDITO. Add the orchestration layer via Galaxy workflows to automate the workflow, which will be expanded to include Ocean Acidification (OA) parameters within EOSC-Marine.	WB partners (Developer users) and End users (scientists) upon registration on the EWB Vlab	Global ocean
Physics: temperature & salinity WB	6-7	3	1	A prototype, that represents a near desired configuration, is being developed at the pilot scale (Mediterranean Sea), smaller than full scale (Global	invited users (beta-testers)	Presently the Mediterranean Sea with the aim to cover the Global Ocean

Name of service	TRL	SRL	CRL	Current Stage and Next Steps (Blue-Cloud funds)	Current users	Geographical relevance
				Ocean). Testing and demonstration of the prototype is being conducted in the VRE.		

Table 2 Blue-Cloud 2026 Integrated Readiness Level

3.2 Sustainability of services up to 2030

In this section for each Blue-Cloud key asset a vision is given of its potential services which could be developed and made available by 2030 onwards and an estimate is given of the related development costs as well as options for securing that funding. The following legend is used for indicating possible funding models.

	EU and other public funding
	Funding coming directly from research institute and academia
	Private contracts and partnerships, other commercial agreements

3.2.1 Foundational Layer

The **Blue-Cloud VRE** and the **EOSC Node European Digital Twin Ocean** are structured as a multi-layered ecosystem designed to ensure modularity, scalability, and resilience. At the base of this architecture lies the **Foundational Layer**, which comprises the **Core and Generic Services**. This layer provides the essential scalable technical tools, including analytical workflows, data lakes, and containerization services, required to support the entire research data lifecycle.

By adhering to the **EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC-IF)** and meeting minimal node requirements, this foundational layer acts as a reliable building block that prevents the need for ad-hoc development for each new application. This ensures that the entire system remains technically cohesive and ready for Smart Federation with the **EDITO** infrastructure.

Figure 1 EOSC Node | European DTO

3.2.1.1 Core Services

The Core Services are essential functional components that align the EOSC Node Digital Twin of the Ocean with the official **EOSC EU Node reference architecture**. These services, starting at **TRL 8**, ensure a trusted and secure federated environment for marine researchers.

- **Resource Catalogue and Registry Services:** Operates as a central, unified repository for discovering, accessing, and ordering scientific products, services, and data using standardized metadata formats;
- **Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI):** Provides a secure, granular access control system (AARC Blueprint-compliant) enabling single sign-on (SSO) via federated credentials;
- **Application Workflow Management:** Offers capabilities to design, test, and execute complex analytical workflows within Virtual Research Environments (VREs);
- **User Space (Gateway):** A dynamic, customizable dashboard serving as the centralized entry point for users to access Node resources and manage tailored Virtual Laboratories (VLabs);
- **Service Monitoring & Accounting:** Includes a real-time dashboard for tracking service uptime and performance, alongside a secure, GDPR-compliant system to record resource usage;
- **Helpdesk:** Provides expert technical and scientific support, comprehensive documentation, and direct links to training programs.

Sustainability

The Core Services are provided and operated by the **D4Science infrastructure**, which is led and managed

by the **National Research Council of Italy (CNR)**. The sustainability of these services is rooted in the long-term institutional commitment of CNR and the multi-domain nature of the D4Science platform. As a robust digital infrastructure, D4Science serves a vast array of scientific communities beyond the marine domain, including social sciences, humanities, and environmental sciences, allowing for significant economies of scale and technical cross-fertilization. This partnership ensures the long-term availability of essential computing infrastructure and the continuous evolution of core services to meet the changing requirements of the EOSC Federation.

CORE SERVICES	
Vision by 2030	The Core Services will serve as the permanent, TRL-9 backbone of the EOSC European DTO node. By 2030, these services will be fully synchronized with the EOSC EU Node’s central monitoring and accounting, providing a seamless, industrial-grade Smart Federation between research outputs and the operational EDITO infrastructure.
Developments needed by 2030	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Implementation of full alignment with the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EIF) for cross-node service discovery. 2. Automated metadata harvesting/synchronization with EDITO DTO. 3. Enhancement of the accounting system to support cross-infrastructure resource credits
Replicability	YES
Is funding by 2030 secured?	 [+] EU and Public Funding [+] Research Institute (CNR)
	GREEN
What needs to be funded to continue the service?	Cloud infrastructure maintenance (servers, storage, networking), software security patching and evolution for AAI protocols, and a specialized technical support team to manage the Smart Federation helpdesk

CORE SERVICES	
Level of investment needed	Medium (Focus is on operational maintenance and technical evolution rather than new fundamental research, but requires stable human resources)

Table 3 Sustainability for Core Services

3.2.1.2 Generic Services

Beyond essential core capabilities, the Node offers a suite of **Generic Services** designed to enhance the research experience and facilitate multidisciplinary collaboration.

- **Interactive Computing and Collaborative Platforms:**
 - **File Sync & Share (Workspace):** A secure, centralized location for storing data with automatic replication, versioning, and seamless connectivity to analytical tools;
 - **RStudio & JupyterLab:** Integrated development environments supporting multiple programming languages (R, Python, Julia) for collaborative, reproducible data analysis and visualization;
 - **Galaxy:** A web-based platform that promotes transparent computational analysis through a user-friendly interface for running tools and tracking history.
- **Spatial and Data Management Services:**
 - **Spatial Data Infrastructure (SDI) Facilities:** Includes tools such as **GeoNetwork** for metadata management, **GeoPortal** for visualizing GIS projects, and **GeoServer** for data sharing via open standards;
 - **Data Management Facilities:** Provides both Relational and NoSQL database management systems and data lake technology to handle large volumes of structured and unstructured marine data.

Sustainability

The Generic Services are also hosted on the **D4Science infrastructure** and operated by **CNR**, ensuring they benefit from the same high-availability and security standards as the Core Services. The sustainability of these tools is further strengthened by their integration into the wider **EOSC Federation**, where they are made available to other thematic nodes and third parties. By serving a diverse user base of over 28,000 members across different disciplines, D4Science minimizes operational risks through a multi-tenancy model. This setup ensures that the specialized tools developed for the marine community, such as the SDI facilities and analytical workbenches, remain maintained and operational as part of a larger, permanently funded European e-infrastructure ecosystem.

GENERIC SERVICES	
Vision by 2030	To provide a globally competitive, AI-ready analytical ecosystem where marine researchers can seamlessly move from data discovery to complex modeling. By 2030, these services will offer a unified Data Science as a Service (DSaaS) experience, fully integrated with the European Digital Twin Ocean for real-time experimentation.
Developments needed by 2030	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Expansion of the federated GPU cluster to 50+ units to support Large Language Models (LLMs) and advanced computer vision; 2. Implementation of AI-assisted workflow composition to reduce pipeline development time; 3. Enhanced integration between Jupyter and the EDITO Datalab for direct model deployment.
Replicability	YES
Is funding by 2030 secured?	 [+] EU and Public Funding [+] Research Institute (CNR)
	Yellow (While the services are operational, the rapid evolution of AI hardware requires continuous fresh investment to remain competitive)
What needs to be funded to continue the service?	Hardware lifecycle management (specifically GPU and high-performance storage refresh cycles), specialized user support for AI/ML workflow optimization, and energy costs associated with high-performance computing.
Level of investment needed	High (Due to the significant costs of GPU hardware and the specialized expertise required to maintain state-of-the-art AI environments).

Table 4 Sustainability for Generic Services

3.2.2 Marine Thematic Services

Marine Thematic Services are a core component of the Blue-Cloud ecosystem, transforming federated marine data into domain-specific knowledge, analytical capabilities, and decision-support resources. By integrating data, computing services, and scientific expertise across multiple marine disciplines, these services enable researchers, policymakers, industry stakeholders, and society to address complex ocean challenges more effectively. This chapter presents sustainability strategy for the portfolio of Marine Thematic Services developed within Blue-Cloud 2026, highlighting their functionality, impact, and contribution to advancing marine research and innovation.

3.2.2.1 Virtual Laboratories

The Virtual Laboratories (VLabs) are demonstrators for web-based open science and are open and available for testing by research communities. They run on the D4Science platform and web environment described above. Each VLab comprises a series of applications for data access and processing, publishing of data results, and managing computation routines as well as services for collaboration, this way providing open science-friendly working environments for its users to analyse datasets and (re)generate research products. Specific training materials including courses to be distributed via the *Ocean Teacher Global Academy* (OTGA) were created for each VLab; three training courses are already available on the OTGA platform as of June 2026.

- [OTGA course VLab 2: Coastal currents from observation](#)
- [OTGA course VLab 3: Carbon Plankton Dynamics](#)
- [OTGA course VLab 5: Global Fisheries Atlas](#)

Additional courses are being developed, during the time of writing of this report, for the following services:

- Vlab1: Integration of Coastal Ocean Observations along Europe (ICOOE);
- VLab 4: Marine Environmental Indicators;
- Workbench: Ecosystem-level EOVs;
- (as a note, an additional course is being launched on the generic service VRE).

In addition to this, the Blue-Cloud VLabs have created strong connections to EDITO:

- VLab 3 Carbon Plankton Dynamics (<https://dive.edito.eu/training> Demonstrator Carbon Plankton Dynamics) training is accessible via EDITO platform.
- VLab 5 Global Fisheries Atlas have onboarded some of their scripts & outputs to the datalab of EDITO. VLab 5 Global Fisheries Atlas has deployed different processes like Shiny apps along with instances of RStudio server IDE configured to explore Shiny apps underlying code (e.g. [Tuna Atlas Shiny app](#) with related code installed by default in this instance of [RStudio IDE](#)).
- VLab 1 Integration of coastal ocean observations along Europe is closely linked to the AQUARIUS project and guarantees maintenance and improvements in their VLab in the next two years.

- VLab2 Coastal currents from Observations is also represented in EDITO with the WITOIL-Cloud for EDITO service (<https://dive.edito.eu/training?search=witoil&path=%5B%5D>), which was deployed in the digital twin actually before the integration with Blue-Cloud and therefore, without the capability to use currents from observations. Nevertheless both applications are interoperable and are capable of performing oil spill simulations.

Coastal Currents Observations VLab

Coastal Currents from Observations

This Virtual Lab provides a service to generate integrate ocean surface current maps from direct and indirect current measurements derived from different sources, High Frequency (HF) radar.

Partners Involved

Data Sources

CMEMS, GEBCO, EMODnet Bathymetry, NOAA, Open Street Map, ECMWF.

The **Coastal Currents from Observations Virtual Lab** enables users to generate integrated ocean surface current maps by merging data from multiple sources. It uses direct and indirect current measurements, including High Frequency (HF) radar, drifter observations, and geostrophic currents derived from satellite altimetry. The integration relies on the DIVAnd (Data Interpolating Variational Analysis in n dimensions) method, which applies physical constraints such as coastline boundaries, horizontal divergence, and momentum balance to improve the reliability of the output.

The main feature of the Virtual Lab is a customisable service delivered through Jupyter notebooks. Users can select a coastal region—depending on data availability and the extent of HF radar coverage, typically ranging from 50 to 200 km offshore—and produce gridded surface current maps in NetCDF format. These maps support Lagrangian simulations, allowing the visualisation of artificial drifter trajectories from user-defined release points. The output also serves as input for the MEDSLIK-II oil spill model, which will be deployed in a Docker container to simulate pollutant dispersion scenarios.

Sustainability

COASTAL CURRENT OBSERVATIONS	
Vision by 2030	Adapting the system to the EDITO platform is a realistic goal. The Ocean Teacher Global Academy self-paced course is available here: https://oceanexpert.org/event/4857 .
Developments needed by 2030	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Improved automatic downloading of datasets ● Generic service/work environment for DIVAnd which can be adapted for different use cases and integrated in separate workflows ● Better integration with Beacon and Copernicus marine in situ datasets ● Work to make it suitable for global analysis, consolidate work done in Work benches and VLab 2
Replicability	Yes
Is funding by 2030 secured?	 [+] EU and Public Funding. Via the new EOSC-Marine project for the surface current products.
	GREEN
What needs to be funded to continue the service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Software maintenance of the service ● D4Science platform
Level of investment needed	TBD

Table 5 Coastal Current Observations Vlab

Global Fishery Atlas VLab

Global Fisheries Atlas

This Virtual Lab's mission is to help making fisheries data FAIR and, by doing so, to provide a more comprehensive view of global fisheries to support informed decision-making and management of fisheries resources.

Partners Involved

Data Sources

FIRMS (RFMOs), FishSource (Sustainable Fisheries Partnership), RAM, and FAO SDG14-4-1 Questionnaire.

The **Global Fisheries Atlas Virtual Lab** offers an integrated view of global fisheries to support decision-making and resource management. It follows recognised standards for data and knowledge management, and it remains accessible to users interested in fisheries data, whether for research, policy, or general understanding. The Virtual Lab is built around two main components: the Fisheries Atlas and the Global Record of Stocks and Fisheries (GRSF)¹. The **Fisheries Atlas** provides a structured spatial data infrastructure. It stores and shares fisheries data in line with OGC standards and assigns Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) through Zenodo. Its main application, the *Global Tuna Atlas*, is developed in partnership with FIRMS (a collaboration between FAO and tuna Regional Fisheries Management Organisations). The **GRSF** compiles and harmonises data on fisheries and fish stocks using standard unique identifiers. It draws from four sources: FIRMS (FAO), FishSource (Sustainable Fisheries Partnership), the RAM Legacy Stock Assessment Database, and the FAO SDG14.4.1 Questionnaire. This approach ensures a consistent view of fisheries data at the global level.

The platform includes regularly updated datasets on catches, stock assessments, and management measures from established institutions. Users can access these data and apply several tools for analysis and interpretation, including interactive maps, visualisation layers, and modelling features. The VLab offers specific services such as a resource catalogue to retrieve and group datasets, a triplestore that enables SPARQL queries to the semantic knowledge base (GRSF), and a MapViewer for spatial visualisation using multiple data layers.

¹ <https://blue-cloud.org/virtual-labs/fish-matter-scales>

By combining structured data access with analytical tools, the Virtual Lab supports users in evaluating fisheries information and developing evidence-based management strategies.

Sustainability

GLOBAL FISHERIES ATLAS	
Vision by 2030	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federation of reference fisheries data sources using standards (OGC standards (INSPIRE compliant), TDWG standards for biodiversity data (GBIF), and semantic Web standards (W3C)); • Tuna fisheries to manage gridded and biological fisheries data in spatial data infrastructures and biodiversity data infrastructures (e.g. GBIF/OBIS); • Use controlled vocabularies promoted both by GRSF and FDIWG to foster semantic interoperability; • Visualisation services for such standardized fisheries data by relying on generic Shiny apps and markdown dynamic reports. <p>The Ocean Teacher Global Academy self-paced course is available here: https://oceanexpert.org/event/4861</p> <p>Part of the FAIR data and code generated by the Global Fisheries Atlas can also be found out of the VLab in widely used repositories. Some products of this VLab have been deployed on EDITO, e.g. RStudio instances or some of the global tuna atlas RShiny apps are available in EDITO at https://datalab.dive.edito.eu/catalog/all?search=tuna (e.g. “Global-tuna-atlas-shiny-app” or RStudio server instance “Rstudio-tunaatlas-pie-map-shiny”). Global Tuna Atlas datasets and code have also been assigned DOIs on Zenodo to better track their use and downloads (Figure 101): e.g. All FIRMS Global Tuna Atlas products (Level 0) and Upper levels of processing elaborated by IRD (Level 2 including fishing efforts). The main releases of the code that are published on Zenodo are directly synchronised with GitHub repositories (version DOIs are being assigned to the main releases of the repositories of the FIRMS Global Tuna Atlas GitHub page).</p>
Developments needed by 2030	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - After building requirements with main users i.e. UN FAO, selected scripts will be updated in GitHub to implement good coding, data management practices and the continuous integration pipelines. These main releases are assigned as DOIs on Zenodo and also shared on FAO Fisheries Catalogue; - Containerization will be improved to foster the reproducibility of the workflow.

GLOBAL FISHERIES ATLAS	
Replicability	Yes, data and code versioning by assigning them DOIs on Zenodo (main releases of GitHub repositories connected to Zenodo) as well as containerization with Docker and renv R package.
Is funding by 2030 secured?	<p>[+] EU and Public Funding. Some funding is already secured by the new EU HORIZON project EOSC-Marine node. An engineer will be hired to allocate more time and improve both FAIRness and reproducibility of data and code. FAO is also expected to allocate time to collaborate on the FIRMS products yearly update.</p>
	GREEN
What needs to be funded to continue the service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Software maintenance of the service • D4Science platform • Yearly updates of datasets
Level of investment needed	<p>The human and economic resources needed are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help desk for VLab users: 0.5 PM to 2 PM/year; • Update of the Vlab products including data generation workflow and outputs (FIRMS level 0 dataset and upper levels of processing) and shiny apps: 1 PM up to 6 PM /year; • RStudio or Shiny apps servers hosting with pre-installed virtual environments: 0.5 PM up to 4 PM/year; • Enhance GRSF with more stocks and fisheries records (as they are approved by GRSF administrators): 0.5 PM/year for publishing approved records; • Refresh approved GRSF records with updated information from their original sources: 0.5 PM/year for updating records.

Table 6 Sustainability for Global Fisheries Atlas Vlab

Integration of coastal ocean observations along Europe

Integration of Coastal observations along Europe

This Virtual Lab implements an environment that is specifically designed to widely expand user’s ability to access, integrate and exploit observations collected along the European coastal ocean areas, with particular focus to the observations provided by the partners of the Joint European Research Infrastructure for Coastal Observatories (JERICO-RI).

Partners Involved

Data Sources

CMEMS, EMODnet Physics, Geology, Biology, Bathymetry and Human Activities, SOCIB Data Repository, IH, PdE, PLOCAN.

The **Integration of Coastal Ocean Observations along Europe (ICOOE)** Virtual Lab provides a platform for accessing, integrating, and analysing coastal ocean observations across Europe. It focuses on data collected by the Joint European Research Infrastructure for Coastal Observatories (JERICO-RI) and other European Blue Data Infrastructures, facilitating the study of coastal processes such as biological connectivity, contaminant dispersion, and the effects of river outflows.

The Virtual Lab offers support to users in 3 thematic areas of relevant impact to coastal ocean researchers and other stakeholders, the presently implemented demonstrator focusing the Iberian Margin global geographic domain. Thematic Service #1 (“Transboundary Currents and Connectivity”) supports users in the exploration of processes promoting long distance transport and exchanges in coastal ocean areas, providing tools for data exploration (extraction and visualization, statistical analyses) and for data integration (transport pathways). Thematic Service #2 (“Extreme Events”) support users in the exploration of impacts on the bottom and offshore structures promoted by major storm events that affected the geographical area covered. Thematic Service #3 (“Ocean Glider”) supports users by demonstrating the added value chain of glider missions from data acquisition to advanced products and visualizations for improved coastal information, integrating ocean state and variability derived from glider transects.

By integrating diverse datasets and providing analytical tools, the ICOOE Virtual Lab aids researchers in improving the understanding of the coastal ocean functioning and in developing informed strategies for coastal management and conservation. Its functionalities are designed to support the creation of FAIR data products, promoting open science practices in marine research. ICOOE Virtual Lab is particularly well adapted to promote a strong articulation with the JERICO-RI community, bringing the expertise of this community in coastal ocean processes to an easily accessed interface with researchers, coastal ocean stakeholders and the general public. The Virtual Lab also connects closely with the AQUARIUS project. Further development of the ICOOE Virtual Lab, aiming to step from a specific geographic area of application to a global domain coverage, will also potentiate a close articulation with the All Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance (AAORIA) initiative, with the potential to support users in a broad range of coastal ocean areas of the Atlantic.

Sustainability

INTEGRATION OF COASTAL OCEAN OBSERVATIONS ALONG EUROPE	
Vision by 2030	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The Ocean Teacher Global Academy self-paced course is available here: link to be added when available ● Thematic Service #1 “Transboundary processes and connectivity along the European margins” <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Dashboard environment (ShinyProxy app) enabling users’ interface for (1) selection of geographical area, time periods and variables of interest (currents, temperature, salinity, sea surface height), (2) identification of data available and access to required datasets, (3) use a range of tools to explore individual datasets (extraction and visualization of the data, statistical analysis), (4) use a range of tools to integrate selected datasets in combined products (transport pathways, poleward slope circulation, interactions with rivers and estuaries). The thematic service, presently available for the Iberian Margin area, is expanded to allow use in a global geographical domain. ● Thematic Service #2 “Extreme events” <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Dashboard environment (ShinyProxy app) enabling users’ interface for (1) selection of geographical area of interest, (2) selection of extreme events of interest for that area, (3) use a range of tools to explore individual datasets (extraction and visualization of the data, statistical analysis), (4) use a range of tools to integrate the selected datasets in combined products (impacts on seafloor substrate, impacts on offshore installations, impacts on the coast). The thematic service, presently available for the Iberian Margin area, is expanded to allow use in a global geographical domain. ● Thematic Service #3 “Ocean Glider” <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Transitioning from a research prototype to an operational service, subject to the availability of specific funding and resources.

INTEGRATION OF COASTAL OCEAN OBSERVATIONS ALONG EUROPE	
Developments needed by 2030	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Improvements of Thematic Service #1 and Thematic Service #2 for wider geographic range, use of full variable range, improved visualization products. - Peer-reviewed scientific paper - Definition of new static product - Articulation with JERICO-RI, AQUARIUS & AAORIA - For Thematic Service #3 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 2026-2027: consolidation and open science (code polishing, Github code publication, integration in EOSC catalog). - 2028: operationalization at SOCIB (automating the generation of grid products and dissemination in SOCIB data services + DOI minting); - 2029-2030: scientific value-add (evolution toward high-impact products)
Replicability	Yes
Is funding by 2030 secured?	<p>[+] EU and Public Funding. Funding from EU project AQUARIUS provide capacity to maintain the pilot demonstrator service for Thematic Services #1 and #2 until 2028, with limited improvements. Implementation of the full vision for Thematic Services #1 and #2 (global coverage, full variable range) is not presently secured by a specific funding mechanism. For Thematic Service #3, the specific funding framework is not currently available.</p>
	GREEN
What needs to be funded to continue the service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Software maintenance of the service; ● D4Science platform; ● Expansion of Thematic Service #1 and Thematic Service #2 to global geographical coverage and complete portfolio of variables; ● User support.

INTEGRATION OF COASTAL OCEAN OBSERVATIONS ALONG EUROPE

<p>Level of investment needed</p>	<p>In order to maintain the presently implemented pilot demonstrator, 3 PMs/year (preferably researcher) would be needed to dedicate support to users. Development of the services to reach the full ambition of VLab 1 to support coastal ocean community along Europe will require additional effort, particularly in the expansion of Thematic Services #1 and #2 to a global geographical coverage and to full variable range. These developments in Thematic Services #1 and #2 will require 35 PMs for development, implementation and operationalization work, to be conducted by a team of researchers during a period of 3 to 4 years.</p>
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Table 7 Sustainability for Integration of coastal ocean observations along Europe Vlab

Carbon-Plankton Dynamics VLab

Carbon Plankton Dynamics

This Virtual Lab provides a service to analyse the relative contribution of the drivers in phytoplankton dynamics in the Belgium part of the North Sea and the northern Adriatic Sea.

Partners Involved

Data Sources

EMODnet Biology/EurOBIS, EMODnet Chemistry, SOCAT, ICOS-Carbon portal.

The **Carbon-Plankton Dynamics Virtual Lab** provides a modelling environment to simulate interactions between nutrients, phytoplankton, zooplankton, and detritus in marine ecosystems. At its core is a [Nutrient-Phytoplankton-Zooplankton-Detritus \(NPZD\)](#) model that runs in both nitrogen and carbon units, enabling consistent tracking of carbon flows through various ecosystem processes. Initially implemented and validated in the southern North Sea, the model has since been applied to the northern Adriatic Sea. This allows users to explore phytoplankton dynamics in different marine settings and examine factors influencing biomass variability.

The system uses environmental input data such as sea surface temperature, salinity, nutrient concentrations (including DIN, PO₄, and SiO₄), and carbon-related variables like atmospheric pCO₂, wind speed, and pH. These inputs inform the model’s representation of primary and secondary productivity, organic matter degradation, and carbon exchanges with the atmosphere.

Sustainability

CARBON-PLANKTON DYNAMICS	
Vision by 2030	Models are freely available on Blue-Cloud and EDITO platforms. It can be replicated for other marine regions. Ocean Teacher Global Academy course is freely available here: https://oceanexpert.org/event/4858 . Model running in EDITO, link here: https://dive.edito.eu/training Demonstrator Carbon Plankton Dynamics
Developments needed by 2030	None
Replicability	Yes
Is funding by 2030 secured?	No
	YELLOW
What needs to be funded to continue the service?	D4Science platform and EDITO platform
Level of investment needed	None for the VLab, some for both platforms

Table 8 Sustainability for Carbon Plankton Dynamics Vlab

Marine Environmental Indicators VLab

Marine Environmental Indicators

The VLab aims to develop a web application that allows users to monitor and assess the environmental status of marine areas, by performing online spatio-temporal analysis with the implemented algorithms, for selected environmental variables.

Partners Involved

Data Sources

Copernicus Marine Service, Copernicus Climate SeaDataNet, World Ocean Database, EMODnet.

The Marine Environmental Indicators (MEI) VLab enables users to monitor and evaluate the environmental conditions of marine areas, providing essential support for decision-making in ocean management. By integrating multiple data sources, the platform offers a unified data analysis service, facilitating online computation of indicators through Jupyter Notebooks or a dedicated web application. This application leverages the VRE Analytics Engine services to generate indicator outputs. VLab 4 represents four indicators (Ocean Heat Content (OHC), Eutrophication (TRIX), Marine Heatwaves (MHW), Storm Severity Index (SSI v2)) and the web application.

Sustainability

MARINE ENVIRONMENTAL INDICATORS	
Vision by 2030	<p>The service implemented inside Marine Environmental Indicators (MEI) VLab can benefit from the experience gained over the Blue-Cloud project and the Blue-Cloud 2026 project, and will continue its evolution with the task “T4.4.7 MEI framework” in the future EOSC-Marine project.</p> <p>The Ocean Teacher Global Academy course is available here (https://classroom.oceanteacher.org/course/view.php?id=1154) and provides description and explanation about the use of the implemented indicators inside the decision process.</p>

MARINE ENVIRONMENTAL INDICATORS	
	Inside the new upcoming technological infrastructure, the MEI framework will provide standard-based components to cover the common and most popular functionalities that different data processing pipelines might need for the final implementation of operational workflows that aim to the delivery of indicators for policy and decision makers working on the management and preservation of marine ecosystems.
Developments needed by 2030	The key elements to allow the development of “T4.4.7 MEI framework” in EOSC-Marine project are related to the design of standard-based reusable software components and services for (application side): the seamless access to input data from BDIs and from Blue-Cloud analytical workbenches, the publication of output data, the browsing and viewing of output data, the management of workflows.
Replicability	Yes
Is funding by 2030 secured?	 [+] EU and Public Funding. In EOSC-Marine project as task “T4.4.7 MEI framework”
	GREEN
What needs to be funded to continue the service?	The underpinning fundamental services that are needed for “T4.4.7 MEI framework” in EOSC-Marine project are: User Space (Gateway), Resource Catalogue and Registry Services, Application Workflow Management, data processing services.
Level of investment needed	None for the VLab, some for the platform.

Table 9 Sustainability for Marine Environmental Indicators Vlab

3.2.2.2 Workbenches

The Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Workbenches provide integrated digital environments that enable researchers to access, analyse, process, and share marine data through cloud-based computing resources

and collaborative tools. By bringing together federated datasets, analytical workflows, and computational capabilities within a single framework, the workbenches facilitate reproducible, scalable, and interdisciplinary marine research. This chapter presents the sustainability plan for workbenches developed within Blue-Cloud 2026.

Ecosystem-level EOVs

Virtual lab leader

Virtual lab partners

The ecosystem-level EOv service provides a machine learning pipeline which allows for the integration and extrapolation of marine observational data including plankton occurrence (for biodiversity studies and EOvs associated with plankton diversity), plankton abundance and biomass (for global ecosystem modelling applications, ecosystem service research, ecosystem health assessment and EOvs associated with plankton biomass), as well as relative reads (for marine microbiology applications, assessments of ecosystem function, blue economies, nature-based solutions and EOvs associated with plankton diversity and community composition, as well as biogeochemical cycling). This service is fully operational on the D4Science environment, and allows for direct integration of data from GBIF and OBIS, as well as environmental information from COPERNICUS. It comes with an application that allows for geospatial data visualization of the service’s output product.

Sustainability

ECOSYSTEM-LEVELS EOvs	
Vision by 2030	Integration of the EOv service into EOSC node European Digital Twin Ocean as a fully integrated service that can access data directly from major marine biological data repositories beyond GBIF and OBIS such as MGnify. Use of the service in scientific, ecosystem management and conservation applications. Potential inclusion of further analysis depths beyond the ocean surface, and potential scaling of the application to higher resolution. Potential expansion of the pipeline to allow for future projections.
Developments needed by 2030	Integration with MGnify data, e.g. within the framework of the EOSC-Marine project. Direct sourcing of environmental predictor data from other Blue-Cloud WBs. Finer spatiotemporal resolution of output products.

Replicability	Yes
Is funding by 2030 secured?	 [+] EU and Public Funding. Partly, through the new EU eosc-Marine project.
	YELLOW
What needs to be funded to continue the service?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration with EBI data repository MGnify; • Downscaling to higher spatiotemporal resolution (multiple depths, higher spatial resolution down to ¼ degree or kilometre scale, maybe: submonthly scale (depending on predictor availability)); • Integration with environmental data from COPERNICUS services.
Level of investment needed	Resources needed for the asset owners to offer a help desk service beyond the end of the project: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 PM/ year (technician, scientific programmer). Potential ORD grants at ETH could be applied for, to maintain helpdesk-type activities, but funding is not guaranteed at this point. In order to further develop the pipeline, the following resources would be needed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 12 PMs (researcher) for further development and incorporation of new data types (funded through eosc-Marine); • 12 PM (data scientist) for integration of service with MGnify (funded through eosc-Marine); • 24 months (researcher) for spatiotemporal downscaling and future projections (unfunded at this point in time).

Table 10 Sustainability for Ecosystem Levels EOVs Workbench

Eutrophication: chlorophyll, nutrients and oxygen

The eutrophication workbench implements an efficient workflow to merge, aggregate, and harmonise multi-source in situ datasets from EMODnet Chemistry, the Copernicus Marine Service, and the World Ocean Database into unified, high-quality data collections generated through a suite of tools deployed within the virtual laboratory (VLab). The VLab leverages Beacon, a high-performance data lake that enables fast subsetting and efficient data delivery, and uses webODV for interactive exploration, preliminary quality control, and data selection, ensuring transparent and reproducible workflows. It addresses the challenge of data heterogeneity by enforcing strict data syntax and semantic

Virtual lab leader

Virtual lab partners

interoperability rules, including dynamic mapping of key metadata entries and controlled vocabulary terms. The processing workflow also includes dedicated tools such as the CWdt duplicate detection tool, which identifies and flags duplicate records and applies File Forge to resolve and deduplicate the data across sources enabling the creation of consistent, multi-source consolidated datasets without compromising information integrity.

Sustainability

EUTROPHICATION: CHLOROPHYLL, NUTRIENTS, OXIGEN	
Vision by 2030	<p>By 2030, the Blue-Cloud analytical workbench for eutrophication will be established as a core, trusted, and interoperable component of the European marine data landscape, providing cloud-based, transparent, and efficient processing workflows, as well as FAIR, ready-to-use, harmonized, standardized, quality-controlled datasets to support the scientific community, environmental agencies, and policy frameworks addressing coastal eutrophication.</p> <p>The vision is to enable:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fully automated, harmonized, and quality-controlled marine data pipelines that continuously integrate information from EMODnet Chemistry, Copernicus Marine Service (CMS), WOD, and other federated sources. Through rigorous semantic harmonisation, the pipeline provides the necessary framework to scientifically validate the integration of heterogeneous data streams.

EUTROPHICATION: CHLOROPHYLL, NUTRIENTS, OXIGEN

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High-quality, ready-to-use eutrophication datasets aligned with MSFD, SDGs, and Regional Sea Convention indicators (e.g., OSPAR, UNEP-MAP). • A virtual laboratory (VLab) that enables reproducible analysis, transparent QC, and interactive exploration through tools like webODV and Beacon. • A trusted resource feeding into the European Digital Twin Ocean (EDITO) for scenario modelling and predictive assessments. • A community-maintained ecosystem, where research institutes, monitoring agencies, and data infrastructures contribute workflows, QC rules, and extensions to new indicators such as TRIX, chlorophyll anomalies, or hypoxia hotspots. <p>By 2030, the workbench should function as a long-term, FAIR, cross-infrastructure service, integrated into EOSC and recognised as the reference pipeline for multi-source eutrophication data preparation.</p>
<p>Developments needed by 2030</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Orchestration of deployed tools to deliver fully automated data pipelines, minimising manual intervention and processing bottlenecks. • Enhanced and expanded metadata and semantic harmonisation to support unified processing of eutrophication and ocean acidification parameters. • Integration with digital twin architectures (e.g., EDITO) to feed modelling layers and support environmental impact assessments. • Strengthen interoperability across RIs, ensuring alignment with EMODnet, Copernicus, SeaDataNet, GOOS, OBIS, and RDA standards. • Upgraded automated QC procedures, including refinement and optimisation of duplicate detection algorithms. • Scale up large dataset handling capacities to streamline the processing and publication of extensive marine datasets.
<p>Replicability</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is funding by 2030 secured?</p>	<p>[+] EU and Public Funding. Via the new EOSC-Marine project</p>
	<p>GREEN</p>

EUTROPHICATION: CHLOROPHYLL, NUTRIENTS, OXIGEN	
<p>What needs to be funded to continue the service?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Maintenance of the virtual laboratory environment (D4Science / EOSC integration), including JupyterLab, CCP, and Galaxy for workflow orchestration. ● Regular dataset ingestion and harmonisation updates. ● QC refinement, including validation of new flags and algorithms. ● Maintenance of deployed tools: Beacon with semantic harmonisation, CWdt duplicate detection tool, File Forge and webODV.
<p>Level of investment needed</p>	<p>In general, the Workbench is highly dependent on human and financial resources as well as IT infrastructure.</p> <p>Providing help-desk support to ensure the maintenance and effective use of the pipeline, as well as the publication of updated EOv datasets, requires dedicated data stewards and scientists. These roles are essential for performing new duplicate checks, applying quality control procedures, and updating workflows. Additional resources are needed to maintain a user-friendly interface and to support the IT infrastructure required to run the pipeline reliably. Continued expertise from data providers is also necessary to update Beacon queries whenever data models evolve, and to orchestrate the suite of tools already deployed in order to achieve a fully automated and user-friendly service.</p>

Table 11 Sustainability for Eutrophication: chlorophyll, nutrients, oxygen Workbench

Physics: temperature & salinity

The Physics workbench lab allows the integration of in situ temperature and salinity data from 4 BDIs: Copernicus Marine Service, SeaDataNet, Argo and the World Ocean Database. A merged instance (data lake) is available in the VLab with harmonized essential metadata information for rapid and efficient data access. The data goes through a statistical quality control (**Alerts Tool**) to ensure quality consistency and through a **Duplicate Tool** providing lists of duplicates and discards. A key tool is **FileForge** capable of converting, annotating and thinning files (QC alerts, duplicates) enabling the **full pre-operational workflow** to generate an added value and easy to use BC2026 EOvs dataset in which provenance and lineage information are fully preserved.

Sustainability

PHYSICS: TEMPERATURE AND SALINITY	
Vision by 2030	<p>The Physics Workbench lab will become an operational ocean physics thematic service which integrates temperature and salinity data profiles, time series and underway data from different BDIs. Additional BDIs will be integrated in line with the data federation approach, with particular focus in the coastal and deep ocean. The data lake synchronization with the source BDIs will provide frequently updated EOVs datasets which will rapidly allow the generation of data products like climate normals and monitoring indicators. The synergy with the source BDIs would continuously improve their FAIRness and content quality, optimizing the service metadata harmonization and products. It will rely on generic services as Beacon, webODV, DIVAnd, semantic harmonization that will fit the thematic service needs, allowing a continuous codevelopment process, for the benefit of the users community. The pipeline tools and their chaining will be optimized together with the VRE configuration.</p> <p>The ocean physics thematic service of the EOSC node “Digital Twin of the Ocean” will also serve the EDITO platform users for their data-intensive applications.</p>
Developments needed by 2030	<p>The VRE resources and the tools need to be adapted to allow the processing of global datasets in all pipeline phases. The semantic harmonization will be further enhanced. A vertical interpolation toolbox and mapping toolbox (DIVAnd) will be included in the pipeline to encompass the generation of climate normals and indicators.</p>
Replicability	Yes
Is funding by 2030 secured?	<div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> <p>[+] EU and Public Funding. Via the new EOSC-Marine project</p> </div>
<div style="display: flex; align-items: center;"> </div>	GREEN
What needs to be funded to continue the service?	<p>All pipeline components need to be maintained, and continuously updated. Its orchestration requires operational management and a service desk which will manage user requests in collaboration with the service managers. A continuous feedback loop engaging on one side the source BDI managers and on the other side the service users will ensure its fit-for-use and fit-for-purpose. A service desk and an operational management group need to be established.</p>

<p>Level of investment needed</p>	<p>The Physics Workbench pipeline will demonstrate the feasibility of data integration from different sources adding value to the present available EOVs datasets, but since the datascape and the technological advancements are rapidly evolving, only a continuous maintenance and update of the operational chain would guarantee its results.</p> <p>The systematic update and release of EOv datasets would require:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Human and financial resources; ● A framework for data managers and scientists to continuously develop semantic harmonization, data exploration/analysis and visualization service (webODV), duplicate analysis, QC tools and mapping tools; ● The data providers (source BDI) expertise to update beacon instances and queries according to the evolving data model; ● The implementation of a user interface to easily run the pipeline. <p>The provision of a help desk support would ensure maintenance & viable use of the Workbench’s pipeline in time is also highly dependent on additional human and financial resources.</p>
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Table 12 Sustainability for EPhysics: temperature & salinity Workbench

3.3. Current sustainability by other projects and initiatives

The long-term sustainability of Blue-Cloud 2026 assets is strengthened through their integration with, and adoption by, a growing ecosystem of European and international projects, research infrastructures, and operational initiatives. These collaborations provide opportunities for continued technical maintenance, service enhancement, community uptake, and alignment with broader strategic priorities in marine research, digital infrastructures, and Open Science. This chapter briefly reviews projects and initiatives that are currently contributing to the sustainability of Blue-Cloud 2026 results, highlighting how ongoing synergies support the continued evolution and impact of Blue-Cloud 2026 results beyond the lifetime of the project.

3.3.1 Hackathon Winners

One of the clearest illustrations of how Blue-Cloud 2026 results are being sustained beyond the project's conclusion comes from the Blue-Cloud Hackathon, where participating teams were challenged to build new services by leveraging Blue-Cloud's existing outputs and infrastructure.

3.3.1.1 TwinTrack

The DTOcean team, one of the winners of the Hackathon, developed TwinTrack², a prototype digital twin for fish movement in the North Sea. Built on the EDITO platform, TwinTrack integrates outputs from the

² <https://blue-cloud.org/hackathon/twintrack-hackathon-2025> and <https://dtotwintrack.lab.dive.edito.eu/>

Blue-Cloud Fisheries Atlas V Labs and Zooplankton EO V Workbench to explore how animal tracking data can be incorporated into broader ocean data infrastructures and used to support early predictive modelling in a Digital Twin of the Ocean context.

The hackathon format proved instrumental. Blue-Cloud resources accelerated the development of TwinTrack as an early prototype, while the process deepened the team's understanding of how Blue-Cloud data products and the EDITO platform can support animal movement modelling at scale. The result showcases the reusability of Blue-Cloud Virtual Lab outputs for marine spatial planning, biodiversity assessment, and open science. Crucially, TwinTrack's impact extends beyond the hackathon itself. The prototype has since been officially recognised as an EDITO test use case, embedding Blue-Cloud outputs directly into wider European efforts to develop interoperable, policy-relevant Digital Twin of the Ocean tools. This recognition illustrates precisely how Blue-Cloud 2026's legacy is being carried forward: not through the project alone, but through the communities, platforms, and downstream applications it helped to catalyse.

Figure 2 Twin Track Homepage snapshot

3.3.1.2 Kraken the Code - OctoPulse

The **OctoPulse project**³ demonstrates how Blue-Cloud 2026 infrastructure is being put to practical use by research teams working at the intersection of open science, marine ecology, and community engagement. Inspired by an anomalous octopus bloom observed off the south-west of the UK in 2025, the project set out to explore how historical environmental data could be used to understand and anticipate such events

³ <https://blue-cloud.org/hackathon/kraken-code-hackathon-2025>

through a collaborative, co-development approach, bringing together fishers, scientists and policymakers within a joint team work to address marine problems.

During the Blue-Cloud Hackathon, the team **used the Blue-Cloud Open Science platform to run a Jupyter notebook retrieving Western Channel Observatory data and generating interactive visualisations with quality-control elements, allowing users to explore both data reliability and environmental patterns over time.** The Blue-Cloud environment proved directly enabling: prebuilt Jupyter Lab environments with all required Python libraries preinstalled **significantly accelerated development**, while the shared, browser-accessible workspace **allowed team members to collaborate from any location without the need for local IT infrastructure.** This kind of accessible, ready-to-use computational environment is valuable for scientists who lack large institutional IT support.

The workflow developed during the hackathon demonstrates how Blue-Cloud can underpin FAIR, open, and reproducible marine data exploration, forming a practical foundation for collaborative hypothesis development and future early-warning applications for hazardous marine events.

The project's reach has already extended beyond the hackathon itself. OctoPulse was cited as a concrete example output in a presentation during an online event on federated data architectures and their role in enabling real-time data for Digital Twins of the Ocean⁴, prompting further interest from attendees around synergies with the broader Blue-Cloud 2026 project. This visibility reflects how hackathon outcomes continue to resonate within the European ocean science community, contributing to the sustained relevance of Blue-Cloud 2026's open infrastructure long after the project's formal conclusion.

This experience has deepened the team's familiarity with EOSC-aligned tools and workflows, building their capacity to structure, format and publish scientific data in ways that support interoperability and integration within federated European research infrastructures.

⁴ <https://ditto-oceandecade.org/news-events/events/ditto-online-event-2026/>

Figure 3 OctoPulse Monitoring interface (snapshot)

3.3.1.3 RugOBSS

Another example of how Blue-Cloud 2026 results are being sustained and built upon comes from the **RugOBSS project**⁵ (also a Hackathon Winner), which monitors invasive macroalgae beachcasts along the Andalusian coast. The team developed a detection algorithm within the Google Earth Engine cloud computing environment and conducted extensive fieldwork campaigns across Andalucía to collect the first-ever in situ validation dataset for remote sensing of this invasive species. This dataset, which captures cover, height, and biomass of beachcast macroalgae, **was made possible directly through the funding and framework the hackathon provided**, and has elevated the project to an international level of visibility.

The team also engaged with Blue-Cloud's 2 Virtual Labs “Integration of Coastal Ocean Observations along Europe (ICOOE)” and “Coastal Currents from Observations” to explore drifting models capable of tracking potential invasion sources. While technical limitations were encountered this engagement produced structured, targeted feedback to the VLab developers, contributing to the improvement of these tools for future users. It also opened channels for collaboration with the broader Blue-Cloud community around more user-oriented ocean modelling tools.

The mid-term goal is for Blue-Cloud resources and the EDITO platform serves as the foundation for sharing the first-ever biomass prediction and beaching event risk assessment maps, giving coastal managers actionable tools to prepare and respond. A final RugOBSS project meeting is planned for this

⁵ <https://blue-cloud.org/hackathon/rugobss-hackathon-2025>

June in Cádiz with 40–50 stakeholders (including municipalities, coastal managers, harvesting companies and regional administration from Spain and Portugal) to present preliminary results and **co-design a transferable tool for both beachcast detection and predictive modelling.**

Figure 4 RugOBSS Invasive Macroalgae Observing Beachcast System

3.3.2 FAIR-EASE

The [FAIR-EASE project](#), coordinated by CNRS, focused on enabling access to FAIR geoscientific data through customised services and virtual research environments. The main objective of FAIR-EASE was to customise and operate distributed and integrated services for the observation and modelling of the Earth system, environment and biodiversity by improving their different components implemented in close cooperation with user-communities, the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and research infrastructures in their design and sustainable availability.

The collaboration with FAIR-EASE contributed to the sustainability of Blue-Cloud 2026 by reinforcing the long-term exploitation and reuse of the Blue-Cloud Virtual Research Environment (VRE) and its analytical services within the broader EOSC ecosystem. Through the deployment of dedicated VLabs (Marine Omics Observations and Coastal Water Dynamics) and the integration of FAIR-EASE components into the Blue-Cloud infrastructure, the cooperation demonstrates how external projects can continue to rely on Blue-Cloud services beyond the project lifetime. This sustainability pathway is further strengthened by the continuation of FAIR-EASE-related work through the [EOSC Node Data Terra](#), particularly in relation to the

consolidation of FAIR, interoperable environmental data services and their integration within EOSC. The Data Terra EOSC Node is the French national research e-Infrastructure for the Earth System, biodiversity and environmental scientific domains supported by several national research-performing organisations and universities. The joint work on FAIR data practices, interoperability, training, and alignment with EDITO and the European Digital Twin Ocean reinforces the positioning of Blue-Cloud as a sustainable federated environment for marine and environmental research.

3.3.3 CLIMAREST

The [CLIMAREST project](#) aimed to restore marine ecosystems from the Arctic to the Atlantic through a holistic, transdisciplinary approach, focusing on fragile habitats and developing a generalisable framework for efficient restoration. The project also emphasised upscaling and integration of restoration tools and protocols for policymakers to enhance climate resilience in the region. The cooperation with CLIMAREST supported the sustainability of Blue-Cloud 2026 by expanding the adoption of its VRE and Virtual Labs within the marine restoration and biodiversity research communities. Through the integration of biodiversity monitoring and human impact data, as well as the use of Blue-Cloud services to support restoration-related pilot activities, the collaboration contributed to increasing the relevance and reuse of Blue-Cloud infrastructures in support of climate resilience and ecosystem restoration. Joint activities on knowledge exchange, training, webinars, and hackathons also help strengthen community engagement and promote the long-term uptake of the services developed by both initiatives.

3.3.4 SUBMERSE

SUBMERSE ([SUBMarine cableEs for ReSearch and Exploration](#)) is an EU-funded project which aims to utilise existing submarine cables, already used by the research and education networking community, to monitor the Earth and its systems. The collaboration with SUBMERSE contributed to the sustainability of Blue-Cloud 2026 by extending the use of its Virtual Research Environment to new domains linked to Earth observation and submarine cable monitoring. Through the planned deployment of a dedicated SUBMERSE VLab and the validation of new services within the Blue-Cloud infrastructure, the cooperation demonstrates the flexibility and scalability of the Blue-Cloud ecosystem for onboarding external services and communities. The exchange of expertise on tools, workflows, and policy implementation pathways also supports the long-term evolution of interoperable and reusable marine digital services aligned with EOSC and DTO developments.

3.3.5 FAME - OSCARS cascading grant project

The [FAME project](#) has been funded via a cascading grant mechanism by the Horizon Europe [OSCARS project](#), a European project designed to foster the uptake of Open Science by advancing FAIR research data and cross-disciplinary services within EOSC.

FAME aims to develop a modular and FAIR-aligned framework for marine Species Distribution Models (SDMs), known as GLOSSA v2, building on an earlier prototype limited to presence/absence modelling.

The collaboration with FAME strengthens the sustainability of Blue-Cloud 2026 by promoting the reuse of its infrastructure and services for FAIR-aligned marine Species Distribution Modelling workflows.

By exploring the development of a dedicated VLab within the Blue-Cloud platform, FAME contributes to expanding the range of scientific applications supported by the Blue-Cloud ecosystem while increasing the visibility and long-term reusability of marine modelling workflows and outputs. The integration of FAME services with the Blue-Cloud is planned for the end of 2026, with subsequent integration into the EOSC catalogue, further reinforcing interoperability and supporting the continued positioning of Blue-Cloud as a sustainable and federated research environment for marine science.

3.3.6 Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (SBEP)

Blue-Cloud 2026 has attracted interest from the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (SBEP)⁶ because it provides operational digital resources that directly support the needs of marine research and innovation projects. Through its federated access to major European marine data infrastructures, virtual research environments, FAIR data services, and analytical workflows, Blue-Cloud enables researchers to discover, access, combine, and analyse heterogeneous ocean datasets more efficiently. These capabilities are particularly relevant for SBEP-funded activities addressing marine biodiversity, ecosystem restoration, climate resilience, sustainable fisheries, and ocean observation, where access to interoperable and reusable marine data is essential. By offering mature e-infrastructure services and promoting common standards for data management and sharing, Blue-Cloud 2026 can facilitate collaboration across projects, improve the uptake of research results, and reduce duplication of effort within the broader European blue economy research landscape.

With this, Blue-Cloud 2026 is listed in SBEP-related call and supporting documentation as a relevant European research infrastructure contributing to marine data access and digital ocean research capabilities, namely in the latest “Proposal for Additional Activities for Cycle 3 of the Partnership”⁷, published in January 2026.

4. Implementation Roadmap

The implementation roadmap of this sustainability plan is linked to the evolutionary path described in Section 2 of this document. Such path is consistent with the “Strategic Roadmap towards building a federated digital ecosystem in support of Mission “Ocean & Waters” into EOSC” (D7.4) designed by the

⁶ <https://bluepartnership.eu>

⁷ https://bluepartnership.eu/sites/bluepartnership.eu/files/documents/2026-02/sbep_advancing_corporate_ocean_data_exchange.pdf

Blue-Cloud 2026 Consortium to guide the future evolution of the Blue-Cloud 2026 infrastructure and services as an EOSC node. The Strategic Roadmap is structured around three distinctive phases (see Table 13). Sustainability for the services described in this deliverable is envisioned throughout these phases, which will see their implementation funded through the Horizon Europe project **“EOSC-Marine: Operationalizing the EOSC Node | European Digital Twin Ocean to Support the EU Mission Ocean & Waters”** (Horizon Europe project 101292903 funded by REA) (Phase 1), CNR funding (Phase 2), and the delivery of the EOSC thematic node as an operational service offered in the framework of the EDITO program, funded by the European Commission (Phase 3).

Phase	Period	Strategic Objective	Expected outcomes
1. Set up (from candidate to production)	2026-2028	To set up and evolve the candidate node as a functional thematic EOSC node for marine research, compliant with EOSC minimal node requirements as defined by the EOSC Interoperability Framework (EOSC-IF), operating robust, state-of-the-art marine-focused Core and Generic Capabilities, based on evolved specifications across governance, operations, sustainability and technical interoperability with EDITO and EOSC.	An EOSC Node “European Digital Twin Ocean” that is fully interoperable with EDITO and EOSC. Clarity amongst the user community as to the role of the EOSC node as a core component of EDITO.
2. Operations at EOSC level	2029-2030	Based on outcomes and recommendations from Phase 1, deliver the node as an operational EOSC service. Discuss and agree on a governance scheme that aligns with the EOSC governance structures and that will ensure full integration of the node within the EDITO governance structure.	An operational EOSC node “European Digital Twin Ocean” offered as a service to EOSC users. A Governance Scheme for continued and effective technical collaboration of the EOSC marine thematic node as part of the EDITO infrastructure and with the EOSC governance structure.

3. Service Sustainability, Governance and Scale Up	2031-2035	To deliver the EOSC thematic node as an operational service offered in the framework of the EDITO program, allowing for effective scale-up of the node through wide stakeholder engagement and onboarding.	An operational service that accelerates the co-creation and further expansion of the European Digital Twin Ocean by facilitating multidisciplinary research collaboration across EOSC and onboarding of valuable, community validated digital assets onto EDITO. Wider user and stakeholder engagement.
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Table 13 Blue-Cloud 2026 Implementation Roadmap

5. Recommendations for future Practices development within EOSC Node and EDITO

Within Blue-Cloud 2026, a variety of best practices already exist in implicit form through Vlabs, WB, and also their underlying core services. However, few of these practices are made explicit; doing so could support their uptake within EOSC and EDITO, as well as beyond the ecosystem for users worldwide. Practices, in this context, are descriptions of how things are done. Practices have a specific goal, a process of steps, as well as prerequisites and expected outcomes. Practices can be assessed on their maturity through an Ocean Practices Maturity Model.

The larger Ocean and EOSC communities can take a huge benefit from Blue-Cloud and EOSC Marine in documenting and publishing the developed practices: they can gain access to trusted, reusable, and interoperable assets (think VLABs, WBs including the understanding of the processes within). These can be further adopted across (ocean data) infrastructures, disciplines and contexts. This enables stakeholders to build on validated workflows, harmonised data pipelines and reproducible environments, reducing duplication of effort and accelerating scientific discovery. Especially for the ongoing use of infrastructure and processes for the Digital Twin Ocean, this ensures that applications are based on transparent, traceable and quality controlled processes, which in turn can increase confidence in outputs and tools. Even more broadly, the publication of practices through the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission [Ocean Best Practices System \(IOC-OBPS\)](#) backed by the IOC through IODE and GOOS, enhances visibility, uptake and community co-development that strengthens long-term sustainability and impact of European marine digital infrastructures.

Blue-Cloud 2026 already developed a range of methods and practices that are, at a varying maturity level, recommended to publish and share.

The three WBs implement structured pipelines for data harmonisation, quality control, metadata standardisation and multi source data integration. They provide well described, mature, end to end

workflows for generating harmonised data from various sources, including duplicate detection or quality assurance. Their handbooks and how-to's provide a great basis to be further developed and published as a practice without extraordinary effort. This could potentially expand the awareness within the broader community and expand the user base. Additionally, many methods, for example a new automated and cloud-based machine learning pipeline to extrapolate different types of biological ocean data developed within the Ecosystem workbench are mostly already published and should be submitted to OBPS.

Comparatively, the V Labs provide opportunities to capture workflow level and domain specific best practices, either within their tools and services, or using the V Labs as a basis for practices for ocean professionals. Distributed over the V Labs, a variety of practices are evident and should be considered to be documented in more detail and published on OBPS and other relevant practice repositories:

- Advanced FAIR data management, semantic interoperability and DOI-based data publication for data stewardship and reproducibility;
- Multi-source data fusion and coastal process analysis;
- Translation of ocean data into policy-relevant indicators;
- Modelling-based practices with open workflows and cross-platform execution

Furthermore, libraries and tools developed in the project can - and partly already do - serve as the backbone for a wide variety of new practices and methods from the broader ocean community. Examples of these would be BEACON (high-performance data lake and data access technology) or DIVAnd (interpolation and data fusion).

Within the Blue-Cloud 2026 project, a new tool was developed to facilitate the thought and documentation process for methods and practices: the “**Ocean Practices Canvas**” (see Figure below). The canvas enables the structured definition of the problem the practice aims to solve, the proposed solution, stakeholders, inputs, outputs and reuse conditions. The goal of the canvas is to improve clarity, transferability and alignment with user needs. Once done, the canvas can also be used as input for the full practice document.

To ensure consistency and usability, all identified practices should follow the suggested format and template of the IOC-OBPS, and provide the necessary metadata and responses to the IOC-OBPS acceptance criteria – this way, they can be included in the IOC OBPS repository.

Figure 5 The Ocean Practice Canvas

Using the outcomes from Blue Cloud 2026, the upcoming EOSC Marine project should continue this path of documenting the efforts within the projects, and should establish a structured way to transform project results like the individual VLabs and WBs, but also the tools and services relevant for re-use by other Ocean stakeholders into published, mature practices. Using the templates and canvas mentioned above will support this transition, allowing the project to start with practice-related work effort from the very beginning.

In this context, practices should be treated as sustained and living documents, continuously being updated through community feedback and operational experience. Blue-Cloud 2026 has demonstrated that sustainability is not achieved solely through infrastructure, but through active communities and reuse across projects and domains.

Looking further ahead, additional efforts should focus on advancing Ocean Best Practices through the adaptation to technological change, particularly the integration of AI and Large Language Models (LLMs) to support automated best practice creation, semantic harmonisation, multilingual automated machine translation, and maturity assessment of practices. The evolution of the Ocean Practices Federated

Network (OPFN)⁸, which is currently in development and aims to interconnect various repositories that host ocean practices, will continue to onboard more nodes, with potentially also including EOSC catalogues as well as EDITO practices. Furthermore, with the maturing of practices, a deeper engagement with standards organisations should be pursued to ensure alignment with global standards – or the development thereof based on project outcomes. Finally, long-term sustainability will also depend on embedding best practices into education and capacity building, including their integration into academic curricula and professional training programmes, fostering a new generation of scientists and practitioners.

6. Conclusion

As Blue-Cloud 2026 reaches its conclusion in June 2026, the focus shifts from project implementation to ensuring the long-term continuity, adoption and impact of its key assets and achievements. Throughout its lifetime, Blue-Cloud 2026 has established a robust ecosystem of federated marine data services, Virtual Labs and Workbenches that support Open Science and advance marine research and innovation across Europe.

This Sustainability Strategy and Plan demonstrates that the future of Blue-Cloud 2026 extends beyond the formal end of the project. Sustainability is supported through a combination of technical integration into established research infrastructures, continued uptake by scientific communities, alignment with European and international policy priorities, and engagement with complementary projects and initiatives.

A key element of this sustainability strategy is the integration of Blue-Cloud results within broader European digital infrastructures and initiatives. The emergence of the EOSC EU Node provides a strategic opportunity to ensure continued access to and visibility of Blue-Cloud services within the EOSC ecosystem, enabling researchers to benefit from interoperable data, computing resources and collaborative research environments. At the same time, Blue-Cloud's 2026 active contribution to the development of the European Digital Twin Ocean through EDITO (European Digital Twin Ocean) creates a direct pathway for the continued exploitation and evolution of Blue-Cloud 2026 assets, methodologies and expertise within one of Europe's flagship ocean initiatives.

Furthermore, the outcomes and expertise generated by Blue-Cloud 2026 are well positioned to contribute to the objectives of the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (SBEP), supporting future collaborative research and innovation actions that promote a sustainable, climate-neutral and resilient blue economy across Europe. Through alignment with SBEP priorities, Blue-Cloud assets can continue to enable data-driven approaches to ocean observation, marine ecosystem management, and sustainable maritime development. Likewise, relevant to refer to the recognition achieved by the UN Decade of Ocean Science

⁸ Pearlman, J., & Simpson, P. (2025). Preliminary Design of a Federated Network for Methodologies in Ocean Observing (MS17). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14946530>

for Sustainable Development (2021–2030), which recognised Blue-Cloud 2026 as an important initiative that supports the achievement of UN Ocean Decade framework goals.

The alignment between Blue-Cloud 2026, EOSC and EDITO demonstrates that the project's sustainability extends beyond the preservation of individual services. Instead, Blue-Cloud 2026's legacy is reflected in its contribution to a broader, interconnected European digital ecosystem where marine data, analytical tools, and scientific knowledge can be seamlessly accessed, combined, and reused. Through these strategic links, Blue-Cloud 2026's KERs are positioned to continue supporting research, policy development, innovation, and societal engagement well beyond the project's lifetime.

The project's achievements have created both the technical foundations and the collaborative networks necessary to support a long-term vision for marine digital services. In this context, Blue-Cloud 2026 should be viewed not as a standalone project that concludes in June 2026, but as an important building block in the evolving European landscape of Open Science, EOSC and the EU Digital Twin Ocean.